

Pilot plant design of a Cascaded PCM storage system

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Abstract

The Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) industry needs cost-effective, high-temperature thermal storage to remain competitive in today's renewable market. This document outlines the design of a pilot plant intended to validate the Cascade Phase Change Material (CPCM) configuration for CST applications. The plant key components include a molten salt tank, a pump, an electric heater, two modular PCM test modules, and an air cooler, using molten salts as the heat transfer fluid (HTF). Operating at up to 600 °C, the pilot plant replicates real CST conditions and allows flexible testing configurations.

The cascade PCM design enhances heat absorption and release when latent storage media is coupled with a sensible HTF. Metal wools are incorporated as heat transfer enhancers within the PCM modules, improving heat flow. The electrified PCM modules provide hybrid capabilities, allowing the system to store low-cost electricity from the grid and generate energy on demand. Currently under construction, this pilot plant aims to validate the cascade PCM approach as a reliable, high-performance thermal storage solution, supporting the CST, and in particular de Concentrating Solar Power plants shift toward efficient, supercritical CO₂-compatible storage systems capable of achieving stable 600 °C operation without salt degradation.

Keywords: Phase Change Materials, Concentrating Solar Thermal, Thermal Energy Storage

1. Introduction

Advancing a research line requires demonstrating that new theoretical concepts hold true when applied to real-world conditions. This validation process is never achieved in a single step but rather follows a structured progression through various stages—from theoretical formulation to commercial deployment. These stages typically include laboratory testing, the development of a pilot plant, and demonstration in a larger-scale facility. This research and development process is encapsulated in the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) framework, which categorizes the maturity of a technology from TRL1 (basic principles observed) to TRL9 (commercial implementation).

Within this context, the HYBRIDplus project aims to enhance Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants by developing an innovative energy storage system compatible with next-generation high-temperature supercritical CO₂ cycles. Specifically, the project advances the concept of cascaded Phase Change Material (PCM) storage by integrating metallic wools to improve thermal conductivity, transitioning the technology from TRL2 to TRL4. To achieve this milestone, the University of Seville, which coordinates the project, is constructing a pilot plant equipped with the necessary components to validate the critical element: the enhanced cascaded storage module. This facility will serve as a key step toward demonstrating the feasibility of the proposed storage solution.

2. Location

The pilot plant is located within the laboratories of the School of Engineering at the University of Seville. This location offers significant advantages in terms of accessibility and operational management, ensuring maximum utilization of the facility. However, it also presents a key design challenge due to the space limitations inherent to a university with extensive experimental activity, such as the University of Seville. For the HYBRIDplus project, a 7x3 m indoor space with a height of nearly 5 meters was allocated. Given this high-ceiling laboratory configuration, a two-level equipment distribution was considered, with certain auxiliary components, such as the cooling system, positioned outside the laboratory. After evaluating several design alternatives, a multi-level layout was selected, taking advantage of the opportunity to utilize the laboratory's exterior façade to extend the overall height of the plant. This design ensures that the entire Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) within the system can drain by gravity into the molten salt storage tank. Consequently, in the event of an unexpected event, all high-temperature HTF is automatically drained into the designated containment area within the laboratory, eliminating the need for manual intervention and improving overall safety.

3. Main equipment

The primary objective of the pilot plant is to test the cascaded storage concept. To achieve this, two PCM storage modules with different melting temperatures will be used, representing two steps of what would constitute a full cascade in a CST (Concentrated Solar Thermal) plant. To accurately simulate the plant's operating conditions, a Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) is required to supply energy to the modules during charging and extract it during discharging. The chosen HTF is the same as that used in commercial solar thermal plants: solar salt, a eutectic mixture of sodium nitrate (NaNO₃) and potassium nitrate (KNO₃) in a 60-40% weight ratio. This solar salt is characterized by its high thermal stability, low cost, and wide operating temperature range, with a melting point of 240°C. With this HTF, temperatures of up to 600°C can be achieved without degradation, provided that exposure to such temperatures is kept within a limited timeframe [1]. Consequently, while this fluid can effectively function as a heat transfer medium

at these conditions, it is not suitable for thermal energy storage at this temperature. In contrast, this limitation does not apply to properly selected Phase Change Materials (PCM), making cascaded storage solutions using conventional molten salts as HTF viable for operation at temperatures up to 600°C.

Since the objective of the pilot plant is to use this solar salt within its sensible heat range, it is essential to ensure that it remains in a liquid state throughout the entire process. This requirement necessitates specific measures to maintain all components of the plant at a sufficiently high temperature, preventing localized freezing of the salt during all phases - especially during plant startup, when the risk is highest - while also minimizing thermal shocks in this phase. To guarantee this, all components of the plant, including piping, are electrically heat-traced. To reduce heat losses, all pipes and equipment are thermally insulated, with insulation thicknesses exceeding 120 mm.

To heat the HTF and bring it to the required operating conditions, a 120 kW electric heater is used. This heater was specifically developed for the pilot plant by SEICO, a member of the HYBRIDplus project. It features a shell-and-tube design, where the solar salt circulates through the shell, while the heating elements are housed inside the tubes. To maximize the plant's operational flexibility, the heater was designed to provide different temperature levels within the operating range of a CSP plant, ensuring adaptability to various testing conditions.

To complete the cycle, the pilot plant requires an energy sink, equivalent to the heat exchanger in the power cycle, to reduce the temperature of the Heat Transfer Fluid back to its initial state after the PCM module discharge. To achieve this, the authors opted for the design of a new salt-to-air heat exchanger, also based on a shell-and-tube configuration, where air flows through the tubes, while the solar salt circulates through the shell. To control the heat extraction from the molten salts, a centrifugal blower powered by a variable frequency drive electric motor is installed. The design of this component presents significant challenges, as it is crucial to ensure that during startup, all system components reach a sufficient temperature to prevent localized salt freezing. To address this issue, CFD simulations were conducted during the design phase to verify that, by incorporating electric heat tracing for preheating and ensuring that the air remains stationary within the inner tubes, all elements of the cooler reach the target temperature within a reasonable time frame. To maintain this static air condition inside the cooler, two guillotine valves were installed at the air inlet and outlet.

Fig. 1. Scheme in 3D of the pilot plant

The HTF is collected in an atmospheric storage tank with the capacity to hold the total volume of molten salt circulating through the plant. This occurs whenever the plant is not in operation or in the event of a failure, as the entire system is designed to be free-draining towards the tank. This was achieved through a careful design of the components, ensuring that a continuous slope is maintained throughout the salt circuit, allowing the molten salt to flow naturally into the tank in the absence of hydrostatic pressure from the pump. To prevent blockages, dead zones, or closed valves, all pipelines and components through which the salt flows were designed with a minimum slope of 1%. The tank is equipped with two electric heaters inserted at its lower section, which are capable of remelting the solar salt in the event of extended shutdown periods, power outages, or failures that may cause salt solidification. Thanks to the meticulous design of the plant, salt freezing is expected to occur only within the storage tank. However, as a precautionary measure, the entire electric heat tracing system has been designed to provide enough power to remelt any localized solidification that may occur within the plant.

To circulate the molten salt and overcome pressure losses within the system, as well as the elevation required to ensure free draining, a vertical centrifugal salt pump is used. This pump has a maximum flow rate of 2.7 m³/h and is coupled to a 7.5 kW three-phase motor, controlled by a variable frequency drive.

The system is controlled through two types of valves: on/off valves and regulation valves. The on/off valves are responsible for defining the correct flow path of the HTF, ensuring that the molten salt follows the intended circuit based on the specific test phase. During charging, the HTF flows from the storage tank to the electric heater, then through the PCM modules, and finally returns to

the tank via the cooler, ensuring that the salt reaches the tank at an appropriate temperature. Depending on the selected test configuration, the valves control whether the HTF circulates through both PCM modules in cascade configuration or through only one module in single-pass mode. Additionally, the pilot plant is designed to allow independent temperature control of the bulk salt in the storage tank, moving the salts through either the heater or cooler, without passing through the PCM modules. The regulation valves play a crucial role during pump startup, helping to manage pressure buildup and ensuring a smooth and controlled operation. They are also used to fine-tune the flow rate of the HTF as it circulates through the pilot plant, providing flexibility in system operation and optimizing performance under different test conditions.

4. PCM modules

The PCM modules represent the core components of the pilot plant, playing a crucial role in validating the cascade thermal storage concept. To experimentally assess this approach, two PCM modules with different melting temperatures will be installed, enabling a two-step cascade configuration. During operation, the HTF will sequentially flow through both modules, replicating the thermal stratification expected in a full-scale system. This arrangement enhances thermal efficiency by optimizing heat extraction and storage across multiple temperature levels.

Fig. 2. Cascade concept to be tested in the pilot plant

A key feature of these modules is the integration of metal wools as a thermal conductivity enhancement method. The inherently low thermal conductivity of PCMs often limits their heat exchange efficiency; however, by embedding metallic structures within the storage material, the modules significantly improve heat transfer rates, ensuring effective energy exchange with the HTF. The internal design of the modules follows the shell-and-tube heat exchanger configuration, with the PCM housed in the shell and the HTF circulating through an array of tubes. The metal wool arrangement is anisotropic, exhibiting higher thermal conductivity in the radial direction than in the axial direction relative to the tubes [2]. This design not only enhances lateral heat transfer but also promotes the formation of a thermocline, improving the efficiency of both sensible and latent heat utilization within each module. To accommodate the thermal expansion of the PCM during phase change, the modules incorporate a nitrogen gas cover, allowing for controlled volume expansion while maintaining an internal pressure of up to 6 bar. For safety purposes, each module is equipped with a Pressure Safety Valve (PSV) to prevent excessive pressure buildup.

A notable feature of the pilot plant is its modular design, allowing the PCM within each module to be drained and replaced as needed. This capability enhances the flexibility of the system, enabling the evaluation of different PCMs under varying operating conditions. For the initial testing phase, sodium nitrate (NaNO_3), with a melting point of 310°C [3], has been selected as the first PCM to be used in the pilot plant.

Several thermocouple sensors will be installed inside each module in the PCM side at different positions. With this sensors, the temperature map of the system at each instant will be obtained. The internal temperature map of the module and the temperature of the HTF at the inlet and outlet will be used to characterize the performance of the system.

5. Control

The control of the pilot plant is designed to ensure stable and efficient operation by continuously monitoring key parameters and adjusting system components accordingly. The cooling of the HTF is regulated through a thermocouple installed at the cooler outlet, which provides a setpoint signal to the variable frequency drive (VFD) controlling the blower motor. By dynamically adjusting the blower speed, the system is able to precisely modulate the heat extraction process, ensuring that the HTF returns to its desired temperature before recirculating. Similarly, the heating of the HTF is controlled by a thermocouple located at the heater outlet, which dictates the power output of the electric heater. This setup allows for real-time adjustments to maintain the required operating temperature and prevent thermal fluctuations that could affect overall system performance.

One of the key challenges in controlling the plant arises from the limited reliability of conventional flowmeters when dealing with high-temperature molten salts. To overcome this issue, the flow rate is monitored indirectly by considering a combination of parameters, including pump outlet pressure, pump power supply and the position of the recirculation valve. This approach provides a reliable estimation of the actual flow without requiring direct flow measurement, which is often impractical in such extreme operating conditions. Additionally, the tank level is continuously monitored using a bubbling-type level sensor, ensuring accurate tracking of the molten salt inventory within the system.

The charging and discharging processes of the PCM modules require a more sophisticated control strategy due to the complexity of heat transfer within the storage system. Instead of direct measurement, these processes are managed based on operation curves obtained through numerical simulations, combined with real-time HTF outlet temperature readings from the PCM modules. These data points allow operators to estimate the state of charge and discharge with sufficient accuracy. Furthermore, the PCM modules are equipped with an array of internal temperature sensors, which provide detailed thermal profiles of the storage material. The information gathered from these sensors will be used to continuously refine and recalibrate simulation models, ensuring that theoretical predictions align closely with actual operating conditions in the pilot plant. This iterative approach enhances the reliability of the control system and improves the overall efficiency of thermal energy storage management.

All thermocouples are type K, with sheaths of 6 mm diameter made of stainless steel to ensure compatibility with the molten salts. The thermocouples are equipped with 4-20 mA transmitters to communicate with the control system.

6. Conclusions

A pilot plant for the HYBRIDplus project has been fully designed and is currently in the procurement and construction phase. This facility has been specifically developed to provide a controlled environment for validating the cascade thermal energy storage concept using Phase Change Materials (PCM). By replicating key operational conditions, the plant will enable a detailed assessment of the thermal performance and feasibility of this innovative storage approach.

Throughout this paper, the main components of the pilot plant have been described, including the PCM modules, heat transfer system, and control strategy, which together ensure accurate thermal management and efficient operation. The flexibility of the plant allows for testing different PCMs and refining the cascade storage concept, contributing to the optimization of next-generation thermal energy storage systems.

Once operational, the pilot plant will serve as a valuable experimental platform, enabling the validation of numerical models, the characterization of thermal behavior, and the assessment of scalability for real-world applications. The insights gained from this project will provide a solid foundation for advancing high-temperature energy storage solutions, particularly in Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants utilizing supercritical CO₂ cycles.

This work represents a significant step forward in the development of efficient and cost-effective thermal storage technologies, bringing the HYBRIDplus project closer to its goal of enhancing the performance and competitiveness of renewable energy systems.

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